

The Effect of Think-Pair-Share Cooperative Learning Approach on Retention among Senior High School Students in Mensuration

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on retention in mensuration among S.H.S. (Senior High School) students in the Yendi municipality. The specific objectives were a) examine the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on gender among S.H.S students’ academic performance in mensuration, b) determine the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on S.H.S students’ retention in mensuration. Two intact classes were used for this study in a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalents control group design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the control and the experimental group from the two schools, consisting of 84 students: 41 and 43 respectively for the control and experimental group. The data collection instrument was mainly test (pretest and posttest). Data analysis were done by descriptive and inferential means. A reliability correlation coefficient of 0.77 was obtain by Pearson Product Moment correlation formula. The study concluded that males and females’ performance improved equally when the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach was implemented. Also, the study revealed that, the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach improves S.H.S students’ retention in mensuration. The study recommends that, pre-service teachers and in-service teachers should be trained to implement “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach in mathematics classroom, as this child-centered approach ensure equity in gender performance and improve retention of mathematics concept, especially in mensuration.

Keywords: *cooperative learning approach, mathematics classroom, child-centered approach, gender performance.*

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Introduction

Mathematics' importance in promoting personal development is attested to by the fact that it is included in school curriculum all around the world. Mathematics proficiency is a key factor for young people's post-secondary education and job prospects (Abubakari et al., 2023; Mensah-Wonkyi & Adu, 2016). As a result, mathematics is regarded as a cornerstone for achieving societies' developmental goals. The development of any nation solely relies on its application of science and technology. The basis for science and technology is mathematics (Abubakari et al., 2023; Mensah-Wonkyi & Adu, 2016). Not only is mathematics the basic root of science and technology but also for commences, agriculture, transportation, health, etc. In Ghana, students in Primary, Junior, and Senior High Schools are required to study mathematics as one of their core subjects. Because of its importance, every student must have a credit pass in the core mathematics of the West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (WASSCE) to be admitted to any postsecondary institution in Ghana.

Mathematics is broad and contains a wide range of topics such as numbers and numeration, algebra and statistics and probability. One of the main aims of Senior High School mathematics instruction in Ghana is to help students to “Understand the process of measurement and use appropriate measuring tools” (Ministry of Education [MOE], 2010, p. ii). This general aim is becoming a mirage to the education fraternity because students continuously perform poorly in mensuration and mathematics in general (Chief Examiners reports, 2018-2020).

In the SHS mathematics curriculum, Mensuration is an aspect of the mathematics teaching syllabus that deals with the calculation or determination of properties of geometric figures and covers perimeter, length, area, volume, circumference, etc. Through symbols, numbers, equations and relations, mensuration explains and gives meaning to the properties of geometric figures. This grants humans a better view and understanding of the environment. For example, the genuineness of the measurement of shapes provides a better way to understand nature in three-dimension (3D).

Abubakari et al. (2023) and Yakubu and Bolaji (2016) asserted that despite students' previous experiences and exposures to measurement as soon as they are introduced to the world, the majority of them still find it challenging to answer mensuration questions. Students' challenges in responding to problems on measurements demonstrate that mensuration is still a tough nut to crack in our senior high schools. Researchers in mathematics education have discovered several variables that contribute to students' low performance and retention in mensuration and related concepts and mathematics in general. These variables include a lack of trained teachers, insufficient teaching resources, large class sizes, and pupils with weak educational backgrounds (Yakubu & B, 2016). However, other investigations have revealed that the most critical variable in teaching mathematics that contributes to students' poor performance is the employment of ineffective teaching strategies (Abubakari et al. 2023; Yakubu & Bolaji, 2016).

The current Senior High School core mathematics teaching syllabus suggests facilitators guide students to deduce the concepts of mensuration. This approach has proven not to be effective in achieving the learning outcomes in mensuration over the years. This calls for an alternative approach as suggested by the chief examiner of WAEC in his recent report to teach the mensuration concept using a child-centered approach like group learning which will encourage interaction among students. The

“Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach is a teaching approach that has been overlooked in teaching mensuration concepts.

It has been discovered that the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach, which Frank Lyman and his colleagues first developed in 1981, helps students understand concepts, enhance their capacity to filter information, express their views, and make conclusions (Abubakari et al., 2023; Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019). The ability of the student to value and comprehend the input of their peers is a crucial component in the introduction of the cooperative learning approach (Abubakari et al., 2023; Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019). Since then, it has been embraced by different authors working on the subject of cooperative learning towards improving student performance. The three levels of student participation are the source of its name, with each level's emphasis on what students should be doing (Abubakari et al., 2023; Agbede & Ba'aba, 2019).

“Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach consists of three steps: thinking is the first one. The teacher encourages students to think by asking a question or make an observation. The question should be thought on by the students for a short while. The second is Pair. It is at this stage that the axiom applies “Two heads are better than one”. Students discuss their responses in pairs with a partner or a desk mate. The most efficient, persuading or standout response is chosen as the answer after they compare their ideas or written notes. The last stage is to share. After a brief period of speaking in pairs, the teacher directs the class to move on to sharing responses (Agbede & Ba'aba, 2019; Abubakari et al., 2023 & Robertson, 2006). The ultimate aim of implementing the cooperative learning approach in mathematics instructions is to improve performance (Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019).

Abubakari et al. (2023); Assan-donkoh et al. (2019) and Regnier (2009) asserted that the cooperative learning method can be used to learn most of the topics covered in Senior High School mathematics curriculum in Ghana. This is because teachers can handle students with different learning strengths using cooperative learning. They looked into how cooperative learning affected the geometry students' performance. Their conclusion affirms that the cooperative learning approach help organizes the classroom environments to suit our traditional environment, where children play and learn by interacting with each other successfully. Mensuration I is one of the primary topics covered in form two of the senior high school mathematics curriculum. According to Abubakari et al. (2023) and Assan-donkoh et al. (2019), mensuration has reportedly been one of the hardest subject areas for students to learn in Ghana's senior high school mathematics curriculum, resulting in poor performance in their final exams, necessitating a study. Unfortunately, the ineffective method of teaching mensuration is still used in many SHS where answering textbook questions is the only way for students to participate in class (Abubakari et al., 2023; Assan-donkoh et al., 2019).

The fundamental aim of teaching is for students to understand and retain the information for practice and implementation. For students' performance to improve it depends on their level of retention of information taught. According to Akanmu (2019) performance and retention of students in mathematics improved with the integration of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach. This according to Akanmu (2019) is attributed to the interactions that occur when students pair and share ideas in the cooperative learning approach classroom. Retention as a function of performance can be boosted when facilitators employ a different form of child-centered learning (Abubakari et al., 2023; Gertrude & Nwanneka, 2021).

Although mathematics is crucial for a country's development, there have been persistent reports of students performing poorly in the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) core mathematics exams up until 2019. Also, the Chief examiners of WAEC reported that candidates find it difficult to answer questions involving mensuration. The most recent of the Chief Examiners' reports (2018-2020), suggested that the concept of mensuration must be well taught using group learning in the 2020 report.

These national data on students' weakness in mensuration reported by the WAEC's chief examiner was affirmed in the Yendi municipality. Observation and interaction of the researcher with the senior high school mathematics teachers and students in the municipality revealed that most student evades answering questions involving mensuration in their semester examination. This observation confirms that the Yendi municipality is not left out in the chief examiner's report. These reports of the consistently poor performance of students need an urgent course of action to be taken especially in the Yendi municipality. Some topics and subject areas have been researched using the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach Abubakari et al. (2023); Hetika (2017); Kaddoura (2007); Sampsel (2013); Kothiyal et al. (2013); Sibirian and Medan (2013) that have proven to be effective in enhancing students' performance and retention. However, the focus of these studies on the cooperative learning approach seems to be overlooked, especially in mensuration.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study's theoretical foundation was social constructivism. Lev Vygotsky's work like the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach over the past few decades, has served as the foundation for a great deal of theoretical work and research on cognitive development, especially what is now known as Social Development Theory (Tudge & Winterhoff, 2010). Social Constructivist, holds that learning is a collaborative venture and that the cultural and social contexts are important. The genesis and justification of all cognitive processes are viewed as social interactions (Abubakari et al., 2023; Bornstein, 2018; Tudge & Winterhoff, 2010).

Since he was convinced that community plays a crucial part in the process of "creating meaning," Vygotsky's views emphasize the necessity of social contact in the development of cognition (Abubakari et al., 2023; Matsuo et al., 2020). Understanding individual growth requires considering the social and cultural context in which it takes place. Social processes are the origin of individual higher mental processes. The share stage of the cooperative learning approach allows students to sit in pairs and interact to co-construct knowledge. Vygotsky asserts that guided social interactions in the zone of proximal development lead to guided learning in which children and their partners co-construct knowledge (Abubakari et al., 2023; Bornstein, 2018). The study further adds that how and what students think as they grow up depends on their environment.

Proximal Development Zone (ZPD)

The first concept of Vygotsky's social constructivism, the More Knowledgeable Other is linked to his second major premise, the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This is a distinction between what a student can achieve on their own and what a student can achieve with the assistance and encouragement of a knowledgeable partner (Bornstein, 2018; Tudge & Winterhoff, 2010). The qualified partner is a more learned

and experienced person like a classmate, senior or teacher who can assist the learner to understand the concept through interaction.

According to Tudge and Winterhoff (2010), the learner should get the most sensitive instruction or guidance in the Zone of Proximal Development to help them develop abilities that they will later use independently and lead to the development of higher mental processes. Peer interaction is another method recommended by Vygotsky for acquiring new knowledge and skill. To enable kids who are less capable advance with the aid of more capable peers, the study advises that educators adopt cooperative learning activities.

Vygotsky suggested that group members should have varying levels of competence. According to theorist this will allow more advanced peers to help less advanced peers operate within their ZPD, which is typical of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach (Bornstein, 2018; Tudge & Winterhoff, 2010). The contemporary interest in collaborative learning is also influenced by Vygotsky's theories. One of the main benefits of social constructivist methods of instruction is the transformation of students from passive recipients of knowledge to active participants in the learning process. Also, social constructivism transforms the role of teachers into facilitators who give directions to the flow of activities in the class.

“Think-Pair-Share” Instructional Strategy on the Retention of Students

Retention is the ability to remember and practice what has been learned. According to Okolocha and Chukwudi (2020), retention is a factor of the mind that preserves information learned. For performance to improve, child-centered teaching approaches which give students the ability to retain what they have learned should be employed in teaching. Performance is a function of retention (Sunday Ugwuanyi et al., 2020). Retention is an important aspect of learning and improves performance on the other hand poor performance is a result of poor retention or forgetfulness (Sunday Ugwuanyi et al., 2020). Through interaction in both small and big groups, the cooperative learning approach promotes student participation in the classroom, which helps them retain the topics they have learned. (Sampsel, 2013).

According to the results of a study by Akanmu (2019) on the impact of the cooperative learning approach on senior school students' performance and retention in mathematics, students who are taught using the instructional strategy perform better. The study also showed that the cooperative approach has no gender-based effects on student performance. Last but not least, the study showed that the cooperative learning approach enhances mathematics retention at all levels. It goes on to say that the method should be promoted in mathematics instruction at all educational levels (Akanmu, 2019)

Ugwuanyi et al. (2020) looked into how senior high school physics students performed academically and the retention of information using the flipped classroom and the cooperative learning approach. The study found that the cooperative learning approach improves recall more than the conventional approach. The instructional strategy has a significantly higher retention score than the conventional method, according to findings from a study conducted by Gertrude and Nwanneka (2021) to examine the impact of the flip classroom and “Think-Pair-Share cooperative learning approach” on students' retention in biology (Gertrude & Nwanneka, 2021).

Okolocha and Chukwudi (2020) researched to determine the impact of the cooperative technique on students' academic achievement and financial accounting self-efficacy.

According to the study's results, retention in financial accounting is positively correlated with the cooperative learning approach. The study also showed a significant difference between students who were taught financial accounting using the cooperative learning approach and those who were taught using the conventional method in terms of achievement and retention scores (Nwaukwa & Okolocha, 2020).

Gender and Participation in Mathematics

Mathematics stakeholder together with gender advocate are concern about the performance gap between the females and male groups in our schools, workplaces and communities. This concern has necessitated researchers to investigate pedagogies that can effectively breach the performance gap. Mathematics is perceived to be an area reserved for only male (Buckley, 2016). This perception is fast breeding into reality in our workplaces, schools and communities, as is rare to see females dominating in these places in terms of mathematics. Students active participation in class is highly influenced by the pedagogy employed by the facilitator. Females are more likely not to volunteer their contribution if a suitable pedagogy is not used to solicit their answers (Aguillon et al., 2020; Buckley, 2016; Carabias-lopez et al., 2023).

Female are more social than their male counterpart. If a conducive environment is created, they are more likely to socially interact very well in groups than males (Nwaukwa & Okolocha, 2020). The “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach allows students to talk to each other in pairs before sharing their responses to the entire class. The pair stage of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning will allow students who feel shy to ask question and contribute in class. Ademiluyi and Fawale, (2022) investigated on the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on the academic performance of office practice students. The study concluded that the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach enhanced the performance of both genders. the study attributed the active female participation to the fact that females are more social and discipline than their male counterparts (Ademiluyi & Fawale, 2022). The female made good use of the social aspect of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach. In a similar study (Nwaukwa & Okolocha, 2020) investigated on the effect of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on students academic achievement and efficacy. The study also revealed that the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach helps female students to participate in class actively due to the social nature of females. This result in the improved performance as in their male colleagues, this again can be attributed to the fact that female students socially interact very well in groups.

Abiodun et al., (2022) and Prieto-saborit et al., (2021) in their study revealed that the implementation of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach in mathematics lessons does not discriminate between genders. This was revealed in their study on the effect or “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on students achievement in SHS mathematics. This shows that the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach can serve as a strategy to bridge the performance difference between males and females. Gender equity in the learning of mathematics by Prieto-saborit et al. (2021) revealed that cooperative learning increased performance in mathematics in an equal learning environment. This help to reduce the gap between the genders.

Statement of the Problem

The most recent WAEC’s Chief Examiner report (WAEC, 2020) suggested that mathematics teachers should encourage group work among students and use geometrical figures to enable them to solve questions involving mensuration and

geometry. Students make choices against mensuration or perform poorly on the topic because they perceive mensuration concepts are difficult to deal with. Abubakari et al., (2023); Yakubu and Bolaji (2016) attributed students' difficulties in mensuration to the use of ineffective and irrelevant instructional strategies that do not enable them to retain and make sense of the concepts they learn. Such strategies contribute significantly to students' low performance in mensuration concepts and mathematics in general. The student's poor performance in mensuration, and mathematics in general, limits their chances of gaining admission into tertiary institutions in Ghana. Addressing these calls for alternative teaching practices with the potential to boost students' performance in mensuration in classroom settings and mathematics in general to achieve the set curriculum goal.

Assan-donkoh et al. (2019) recommended in their study that cooperative learning strategies should be used in mathematics instructions to bridge the difference among low, medium and high achievers. A study by Okolocha and Chukwudi (2020) to determine the effect of the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach on students' academic performance and retention in financial accounting in secondary school revealed that the instructional strategy improved academic performance and retention among students. Despite this data available, this cooperative learning approach has been overlooked in teaching mensuration in classroom settings in the Yendi Municipality. This necessitated the study to investigate the potential effect of the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach on students' performance and retention in mensuration in the Yendi Municipality of the Northern Region of Ghana.

Specific Research Objectives

This study was designed to:

1. Examine the effect of "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach on gender among SHS students' academic performance in mensuration
2. Determine the effect of the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach on SHS students' retention in mensuration.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to fulfill the study's objectives:

1. What is the effect of the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach among gender on SHS students' academic performance in mensuration?
2. What is the effect of the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach on SHS students' retention in mensuration?

Hypotheses

To determine the effect of using the "Think-Pair-Share" cooperative learning approach in teaching on students' performance and retention in mensuration, the following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to answer research questions one, two respectively.

1. H_{O1} : there is no significant difference between the performance of SHS students in mensuration among gender.
2. H_{O2} : there is no significant difference between the retention score of SHS students in mensuration in the control and experimental group.

Research Design

Quasi-experimental non-equivalent pre-test-post-test control group design was adopted for this study, considering the respondents of this study who sits in intact classes. This design is a common method for quasi-experimental, where the experimental and control groups are chosen without using randomization (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2013). Both groups received pre-test and post-tests in this design, but only the experimental group received treatments (intervention) in between the two tests.

Participants

The population of the study comprised of public senior high schools in one municipality of the Northern region of Ghana. Census sampling technique was used to select the only two (2) public senior high schools in the municipality. The two schools had a student population of 2891. The target population was the Form two students of the two schools made up of 15 intact classes with a population of 759. Two intact classes from the 15 Form two classes were selected by a simple random sampling technique. The Form two classes were selected because Mensuration I is taught at that level. The sampled classes had 84 students: 43 for the experimental and 41 for control groups. The choice of experimental and control groups was by simple random sampling.

Research Instruments

The sampled behavior to test was students' mastery and retention level of mensuration I concepts. Tests are used basically to ascertain the achievements of a stated objective (Sugawara & Nikaido, 2014). The test is appropriate because according to Adom et al., (2020) they are used to measure the level of learners' understanding. This study employed a teacher-made test in mensuration I, which is constructed by the researcher. This was appropriate because it allows the teacher to test learners based on the specific objectives of lessons in this case mensuration concepts. The test was made up of 30 objective questions drawn from the last ten years' test items of the West African examination council mensuration I questions. Participants were tasked to choose the correct answer from possible answers A, B, C and D that best answered each item in the test. The questions were given to a committee of mathematics teachers to scrutinize and make recommendations. Their recommendations were considered and corrections were affected. Using the Pearson Product Moment correlation formula, a correlation coefficient of 0.77 was calculated. The correlation coefficient demonstrated that there was a very strong positive association between the students' test results.

Intervention

The intervention (treatment) lasted for four weeks. The researcher used the cooperative learning approach to teach mensuration I to the experimental group. The researcher developed a lesson plan incorporating the cooperative learning approach. The lesson plan was then reviewed by the department head for mathematics at the school and the researcher's supervisor. The cooperative learning approach was well-rehearsed by the researcher to ensure its proper implementation in the mensuration lesson delivery in the experimental group. The researcher similarly instructed the control group in mensuration I using the conventional teaching strategy. The conventional method for this study was the use of a marker board and markers where the teacher becomes an active speaker and the students become passive receivers of information.

Data Collection Procedure

Permission was granted by the school authority after the required ethical consideration. The pretest was administered to the experimental and control groups during the same week (a week before the start of the intervention). The researcher personally conducted the test. The printed test items were distributed to the class in their normal class settings (intact classes) in the two schools. The test lasted for 90 minutes (1 hour 30 minutes). Participants' scripts were collected after the time allocated for the test and marked. Each correct answer was awarded one mark, totaling 30 marks for the test. The pre-test was to determine the starting points (entry-level) of the two groups.

At the conclusion of the intervention period, the post-test was given to both the experimental and control groups. For the post-test, the questions from the pre-test were rearranged. The test was supervised by the researcher and the regular teachers in the school.

Two weeks after administering the posttest, the researcher reshuffled the posttest and administered it to the same participants to get their retention score within the two weeks' space. The interval was two weeks to reduce maturation and history effect on the test scores of students used for the study.

Data Analysis

Organizing and evaluating data to find answers to research questions requires a systematic application of statistical and logical methods. Descriptive statistics were used to determine the pre-test and post-test average scores for the experimental and control groups. The mean and standard deviation of the scores from the pretest and posttest were utilized to determine whether there are any differences between the two tests. Independent sample and paired sample t-test were used to draw conclusions and make decisions.

Pre-Test Performance of Students

The pre-test was to ascertain if participants in the experimental and control groups exhibited comparable mensuration skills before the intervention, a pre-test on mensuration was conducted. Participants' scores were analyzed descriptively and results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Students' Performance in the Pre-test (n=35)

Statistics	Control	Experimental	Difference
Mean	8.94	9.54	0.60
Standard Deviation	3.69	3.81	0.12

From Table 1, the mean and standard deviation for the control and experimental groups are (M=8.94; SD=3.69) and (M=9.54; SD=3.81) respectively. The mean scores of the groups have a difference of 0.60 suggesting the scores are centered around each other and affirmed by the almost equal standard deviation of 3.69 and 3.81, a difference of 0.12 indicating that the two groups' scores are less spread from each other. To determine whether the difference in means between the control and experimental groups' pre-test results was statistically significant, an independent sample t-test was performed. The results of the independent sample t-test are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Result of Independent Sample T-Test for the Control and Experimental Groups of the Pre-Test

	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal Variance Assumed	0.594	1.130	68	0.263
Equal Variance Not Assumed		1.130	67.859	0.263

From Table 2, since the sig. value ($0.594 > 0.05$) is greater than the α level under Levene's test for equality of variance, the sig. (2-tailed) of 0.263 on the first line, equal variance assumed was used for this study. The mean scores of the experimental group and the control group do not significantly differ from one another since the sig. (2-tailed) of 0.263 was greater than the 0.05 alpha level. Also, a calculated Cohens d effect size of 0.283 was obtained indicating a small effect (Louis et al., 2018). The results suggest that individuals in both groups performed equally well in mensuration prior to the intervention. Therefore, any variation in the two groups' mensuration performance following the intervention, if it exists, must be due to the intervention.

Normality Test for Control and Experimental Group of Pretest

The use of parametric or non-parametric statistics for further statistical analysis in the study depended on the normality and homogeneity assumptions of the pretest data. Consequently, the Shapiro-Wilk test was performed and the results presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Shapiro-Wilk test for Normality of the Control and Experimental Groups

Group	Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	0.962	35	0.255
Experimental	0.977	35	0.674

Table 3 shows the control group's normality score of 0.962 and a significance level of 0.255 indicating the results were normally distributed since the sig. value of 0.255 was greater than 0.05. Similarly, the experimental group's normality value of 0.977 and a significance value of 0.674 indicated a normal distribution of the data since the sig. value of 0.674 was greater than 0.05. In conclusion, the pretest data of both groups were normally distributed. Since the data of both groups were normally distributed, the test of homogeneity of variance between the groups was conducted using SPSS 25 and the result presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Result of Test of Homogeneity of Variance between Control and Experimental Groups

Levene statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
0.287	1	68	0.594

Table 4, shows the Levene statistics (F value) for the pretest as 0.287 with a sig. value of 0.594. Since the sig. value of 0.594 is greater than the alpha level ($0.594 > 0.05$), then the pretest data of both groups (control and experimental) have the same variance. In other words, the pretest data of the control and experimental groups were

homogeneous. Based on the analysis of the normality and homogeneity tests, the control and experimental groups had the same starting proficiency in mensuration.

The performance of students in the pretest by gender was also analysed to determine entry level of both gender in the experimental group and the result presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Students' Performance by Gender in the Experimental Group in the Pre-Test (n=35)

Statistics	Males	Females	Difference
Mean	6.47	7.32	0.85
Standard Deviation	1.53	1.69	0.16

From Table 5, the mean and standard deviation for the males and females in the experimental group are (M=6.47; SD=1.53) and (M=7.32; SD=1.69) respectively. The mean scores of the groups have a difference of 0.85 suggesting the scores are centered around each other and affirmed by the almost equal standard deviation of 1.53 and 1.69, a difference of 0.16 indicating that the two groups' scores are less spread from each other. To determine whether the difference in means between the male and female in the experimental groups pre-test results was statistically significant, an independent sample t-test was performed. The results of the independent sample t-test are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Result of Independent Sample T-Test for the Genders in Experimental Group of the Pre-Test

	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal Variance Assumed	0.972	1.480	33	0.148
Equal Variance Not Assumed		1.498	29.186	0.145

From Table 6, since the sig. value (0.972>0.05) is greater than the α level under Levene's test for equality of variance, the sig. (2-tailed) of 0.148 on the first line, equal variance assumed was used for this study. The mean scores of the males and the females in the experimental group do not significantly differ from one another since the sig. (2-tailed) of 0.148 was greater than the 0.05 alpha level. Also, a calculated Cohens d effect size of 0.174 was obtained indicating a small effect (Louis et al., 2018). The results suggest that the genders in experimental group performed equally well in mensuration prior to the intervention. Therefore, any variation in the two groups' mensuration performance following the intervention, if it exists, must be due to the intervention.

Normality Test for Males and Females in the Experimental Group of Pretest

The pretest data were analyzed to determine whether the data were normally distributed and homogeneous. The normality test was to determine the distribution of students' pretest data between the groups. The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed and the results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Results of Shapiro-Wilk test for Normality of the Males and Females in the Experimental Groups

	Statistic	df	Sig.
Male	0.673	21	0.125
Female	0.779	14	0.574

Table 7 shows the male group's normality score of 0.673 with a significance level of 0.125. The male group's pretest results were normally distributed because the significance value of 0.125 was greater than 0.05. Moreover, the experimental group's normality value is 0.669, with a significance value of 0.324. The experimental group's pretest data had a normal distribution because the significance value of 0.324 was higher than 0.05. In conclusion, the pretest data of the two groups were normally distributed.

The test of homogeneity of variance between the groups was conducted using SPSS 25 and the result presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Result of Test of Homogeneity of Variance between Males and Females in the Experimental Group

Levene statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
0.177	1	33	0.328

Table 8, shows the Levene statistics (F value) for the pretest as 0.177 with a sig. value of 0.328. Since the sig. value of 0.328 is greater than the alpha level ($0.328 > 0.05$), then the pretest data of both groups (male and female) have the same variance. In other words, the pretest data of the males and females in the experimental group were homogeneous. Based on the analysis of the normality and homogeneity tests, the males and females in the experimental group had the same starting proficiency in mensuration.

What is the effect of the “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach among gender on SHS students’ academic performance in mensuration?

After the pre-test, the intervention lasted for four weeks. A post test was conducted after the intervention period to both control and experimental group using the same set of questions. This was to ascertain the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning approach on gender in the experimental group. Table 9 represents the results of the males and females in the experimental group.

Table 9. Results of the Males and Females in the Experimental Group

Statistics	N	Mean (\bar{x})	S.D
Males	21	2.53	1.08
Females	14	3.05	2.23
Difference	-	0.52	1.15

Table 9 indicates that the mean and standard deviation of the males and the females of the experimental group are ($\bar{x} = 2.53$, $SD = 1.08$) and ($\bar{x} = 3.05$, $SD = 2.23$) respectively. This indicated a mean difference of 0.52 between the males and the females. This tends to suggest that the performance of the students did not differ

among both gender with the experimental group. This suggestion was affirmed by difference in their standard deviation of 1.15. To assess the statistical significant difference between the males and females performance, a paired(dependent) sampled t-test was conducted. H_{O1} : there is no significant difference between the performance of SHS students in mensuration among gender. An alpha level of 0.05 was used to test this hypothesis and the result presented in table 10.

Table 10. Result of Paired Sample T-Test for the Think and Pair Stage in the Experimental Group

Stage	\bar{x} Difference	SD	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Eta-Square
Think-Pair	10.47	12.79	-3.571	18	0.002	0.82

The paired sample t test from Table 10 showed that the mean difference and standard deviation for the males and females were ($\bar{x} = 3.41, SD = 7.32$). The calculated $t(18)=1.096$ and $\text{sig. (two tailed)}=0.105$. The difference in the mean score between the males and the females is not statistically significant, since the sig. value of 0.105 was greater then the alpha level of 0.05. Also, an effect size of 0.052 was calculated indicating a small effect according to Cohen d t-test effect size (Louis et al., 2018). The null hypothesis one was accepted base on the analysis. Hence there is no significant difference between the performance of SHS students in mensuration in the males and females in the experimental group. In conclusion, it is discovered that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach offer both males and females the equal learning environment of learning as discovered by (Akanmu, 2019).

What is the effect of “Think-Pair-Share” cooperative learning on SHS students’ retention in mensuration?

Two weeks after the posttest, the researcher administered a retention test to both the control and experimental groups. This test was to determine the effect of the cooperative learning approach on students’ retention in mensuration concepts. The posttest instrument was used in the retention test. The retention test was marked out of 30 marks. The descriptive statistics of the results are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Result of Descriptive Statistics for the Retention of the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Post-test \bar{x}	Post-test SD	Retention \bar{x}	Retention SD	Mean (\bar{x}) loss
Control	9.89	3.42	7.60	2.13	2.29
Experimental	15.80	4.44	14.32	3.41	1.48

Table 4.11 shows that the mean scores of students in the control group in the posttest and retention test are 9.89 and 7.60 respectively, a mean loss of 2.29. Also, the mean scores of the post-test and retention test of the experimental group were 15.80 and 14.32 respectively, with a mean loss of 1.48. This shows that the control group's mean loss was higher than the experimental group's.

An independent sample t-test was used to assess whether the differences in retention scores between the control and experimental groups were statistically significant at 0.05 alpha level and the results presented in Table 12.

H_{O_2} : There is no significant difference between the retention of SHS students in mensuration in the control and experimental group.

Table 12. Result of Independent Sample T-Test of Retention Test of the Control and Experimental group

Group	\bar{x}	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Eta-square
Control	7.60	2.13	9.855	67	0.001	1.527
Experimental	14.34	3.41				

The independent sample t-test results in Table 12 indicate that the retention test of the experimental group ($\bar{x} = 14.34, SD = 3.41$) was significantly greater than the control group ($\bar{x} = 7.60, SD = 2.13$); $t(67) = 9.855$; $p = 0.001$. Since the sig. value is less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the retention test of the control and experimental group. A calculated effect size (Cohen's d) of 1.527 was obtained, indicating that the magnitude of the difference was very large and did not occur by chance (Louis et al., 2018). Based on this finding the null hypothesis two of this study was rejected. The retention of senior high school pupils in the experimental group and the control group as a result differs significantly in terms of mensuration. This means that students who were taught mensuration using the cooperative learning approach in the experimental group retained the mensuration concepts more than the students in the control group.

Discussion

It is discovered from hypothesis one that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach offer both males and females the equal learning environment of learning as discovered by (Akanmu, 2019) in other words the implementation of the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach does not discriminate in terms of performance between genders. This revelation indicates that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach can be use as an intervention to bridge the gap in performance between the females and their male counterpart.

The findings is supported by an earlier study by Ademiluyi and Fawale, (2022) which revealed that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach enhanced the participation and performance of the females and male. Female especially student do not want to be intimidated due to their level of shyness. If they are guaranteed of a conducive leaning approach like the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach, where they are comfortable to discuss in pair for the necessary correction to be made before presenting to the entire class. This revelation is also in consonance with an earlier work which revealed that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach help students to participate actively in class due to the social aspect of the approach (Nwaukwa & Okolocha, 2020)

The study again agrees with Abiodun et al. (2022) and Prieto-saborit et al. (2021) whose work revealed that the think-pair-share cooperative learning approach does not discriminate between the genders in terms of participation and performance. Ultimately by this approach, the concerns of mathematics educators and gender advocates will become concerns of the past.

The finding of hypothesis two revealed that students in the experimental group who received instructions in the cooperative learning approach retained mensuration lessons better than their counterparts in the control group who received instruction in the conventional method. This revelation can be attributed to the knowledge-sharing nature of the cooperative learning approach. As students share knowledge and interact at the pair stage, they can consolidate their mensuration concepts.

The findings of this study agree with an earlier study by Gertrude and Nwanneka (2021) who focused their study on the flip classroom and cooperative learning approach to students retention in biology. The study revealed that the cooperative learning approach enhanced students' retention ability more significantly than the flip classroom. Similarly, a study by (Akanmu, 2019) revealed that the students who received instruction in the cooperative learning approach retention were higher than the students in the control group. Also, Okolocha and Chukwudi (2020) in an earlier study found that the cooperative learning approach enhanced the retention ability of students in financial accounting.

On the contrary Ugwuanyi et al. (2020) disagrees with this finding when their comparative study discovered that the flip clip class retained students' performance more than the cooperative learning approach.

Conclusion

This study reveals that the cooperative learning approach is a medium of instruction where both the male and female performance improves equally. This shows that both genders involve themselves actively during lesson that integrate this particular approach. Potentially this approach will eventually bridge the performance gap between the males and female counterpart in mensuration and mathematics at large. As part of the revelation, the cooperative learning approach also enhanced the retention of senior high school students in mensuration. This means that when students are taught using the cooperative learning approach, they do not easily forget as in the conventional method. Previous studies are also in support of the use of this cooperative learning approach in improving students' performance and retention in mathematics and other related subject areas.

Recommendations

Following the revelation of this study, it was recommended that facilitators should integrate the Think-Pair-Share cooperative learning approach in mathematics lessons. The pre-service teachers should be trained and sensitized on the proper implementation of this approach in mathematics lesson. In-service teachers should be trained through workshops, professional learning communities or insets to sensitize classroom teachers on these new teaching strategies.

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